

D7.1 - DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN V1

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Abstract

The transition from linear fossil-based systems to circular and bio-based systems represents an opportunity and a suitable pathway for achieving several SDGs. Indeed, circular bio-based systems depict a great opportunity to reconcile sustainable long-term growth with environmental protection through the prudent use of renewable resources for industrial purposes. This needed transition is a complex process, which does not simply require innovative technologies from the supply-side, but also societal transformations based on a multi-actor process. The circular bioeconomy meta-sector may be a good candidate to put forward a new economic model, which requires transformative policies, purposeful innovation, access to finance, risk-taking capacity as well as new and sustainable business models and markets. However, a critical assessment of the environmental, social and economic impacts of the current linear fossil-based economy, as well as of the improvement potential associated with circular bio-based systems, is needed to underpin the identification of policy priorities. Bearing this in mind, SUSTRACK is a three-year project aimed at supporting policymakers in their efforts to develop sustainable pathways to replace fossil and carbon-intensive systems with sustainable circular and biobased systems (at the EU and regional scale), contributing to achieving the European Green Deal's objectives. This will be done by: identifying environmental, economic and social limits of a linear carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy; improving existing assessment methodologies; assessing the environmental, social and economic impacts of the EU's current linear fossil-based economy; comparing multiple transition scenarios focusing on the most carbon intensive sectors; identifying priorities according to scenarios analysed in the project and develop guidelines and policy recommendations.

Disclaimer

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Deliverable information		
Nature of the deliverable:		DMP
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web	x
CL	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
CO	Confidential to SUSTRACK project and Commission Services	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

DMP: Data management plan

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

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6	UNIVERSITEIT GENT	UGENT	BE
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Data Management Plans (DMPs) are a **crucial element** of good data management as they provide the description of its life cycle, following the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable) data principle. DMPs **include information** on:

- How the data will be handled (how it will be described, managed and stored) both during and after the end of the project;
- What data will be collected, processed and/or generated by the project;
- Which methodology and standards will be used;
- Whether data will be shared/made open access and;
- How data will be protected and preserved (including after the completion of the project).

This document constitutes the initial version of the SUSTRACK Data Management Plan (DMP) and has been elaborated as **deliverable (D) 7.1 (due month 6 being the output of task (T) 7.4)** as part of the activities of Work Package (WP) 7 “Project Management” in the framework of SUSTRACK project. This initial version will work as a living document for the whole duration of the project, hence it will be updated and further elaborated to reflect developments to have an accurate and comprehensive plan at any time throughout the project. The final version of DMP will be delivered by the end of the project (M36). The structure has been drafted in line with the European Commission’s Data Management Plan Template¹, with some additional information adapted to the particular characteristics of SUSTRACK.

Based on the objectives and expected outcomes of SUSTRACK, it became evident that in order to generate meaningful insights to feed into the project while fuelling the co-creation and delivery of real demand-driven and evidence-based results, SUSTRACK entails several activities involving collection, production and processing of data. For Independent tasks, data should be stored after collection/generation and after processing. When processing it is mandatory to archive the SOP and keep the process traceability, e.g. which initial data has been processed, and which methods have been applied. Accordingly, the objective of this document is to collect, analyse and share the initial set up of rules for internal communication, and to have a common approach to how to gather, store and manage the data properly (metadata - such as {date, author, affiliation, version}, where, how, who, title, version, revisions, use and storage etc.).

This document includes the description of:

¹ <https://enspire.science/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/Horizon-Europe-Data-Management-Plan-Template.pdf>

- Data types and how this data will be collected, processed, maintained and shared during and after the end of the project;
- FAIR data management;
- Data Security;
- Preferred repositories to archive published data
- Metadata and vocabulary
- Social, Ethical, Legal, and Privacy concerns.

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List of Abbreviations	
Abbreviation/Acronym	Description
AB	Advisory Board
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
CS	(EU and CS level)
DCMI	Dublin Core Metadata Initiative
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
EEA	European Economic Area
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EUROSTAT	European Statistical Office
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GEM	Green Economy Model
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
IP	Internet Protocol
ISBN	International Standard Book Number
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ISP	Internet Service Provider
KB	Kilobyte
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
NAS	Network Attached Storage
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
PIDs	Persistent Identifiers
QA	Quality Assurance
QC	Quality Control
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprises
WP	Work Package

1. INTRODUCTION

The current document constitutes the initial version of the Data Management Plan (DMP), elaborated as a deliverable (D) 7.1. of the SUSTRACK project, which has received funding from the European Union's (EU) Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 101081823.

The **consortium** of SUSTRACK consists of **11 partners across 6 different European countries**. All the consortium partners **adhere to sound data management principles** to ensure that the meaningful data collected, processed and/or generated throughout the duration of the project is well-managed, archived and preserved, in line with the structure and guidelines of the [Horizon Europe Data Management Plan Template](#).

Along these lines, this initial version of the DMP aims to achieve the following objectives:

- Describe the data management life cycle for the data to be collected and/or generated in the framework of SUSTRACK, serving as the key element for good data management.
- Outline the methodology employed to ensure the sound management of the data collected, and/or generated as well as to make them Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR).
- Provide information on the data that will be collected and/or generated and the way in which they will be handled during and after the end of the project, along with the standards applied to this end.
- Provide details on how the data will be made openly accessible and searchable to interested stakeholders as well as their curation and preservation.
- Present information on the resources to be allocated so as to make data FAIR clearly identifying responsibilities pertaining to data management, while addressing data security and ethical aspects.

With the above in mind, this initial version of **the DMP is structured in 8 distinct chapters**, as follows:

Chapter 1 presents the description of the SUSTRACK context and outlines the objectives and structure of the DMP.

Chapter 2 defines the purpose and objectives of the SUSTRACK activities leading to the data collection and generation processes. It also outlines data types and formats, origin and relevant stakeholders that might utilise them.

Chapter 3 describes the processes followed to ensure FAIR data management in the framework of SUSTRACK.

Chapter 4 introduces data quality assurance processes.

Chapter 5 plans for the FAIR management of other research outputs (digital or physical) that may be generated or re-used by the beneficiaries throughout the project.

Chapter 6 provides an overview of the resources to be used and the respective data management responsibilities.

Chapter 7 underlines the data security strategy followed by the SUSTRACK team.

Chapter 8 addresses ethical aspects involved under the scheme of SUSTRACK regarding the collected/generated data.

Chapter 9 concludes with the next steps foreseen in the framework of the project with respect to its data management plan.

The structure has been drafted in line with the European Commission's Data Management Plan Template with some additional information adapted to the particular characteristics of SUSTRACK. The DMP is not a fixed document rather it will evolve as a living document during the lifespan of the project and will be further elaborated and updated at least once more throughout the duration of SUSTRACK (i.e., as D7.2 at M36). Additional *ad-hoc* updates may be realised (if necessary), in order to include new data, better detail and/or reflect changes in the methodology or other aspects relevant to their management (such as costs for making data FAIR, size of data, etc.), changes in consortium policies and plans or other potential external factors. PEDAL CONSULTING SRO (PC) is responsible for the elaboration of the DMP and with the support of all partners will update and enrich it when required.

Annexed in the document are (i) the project's Privacy Policy (Annex I), the templates for the (ii) Informed Consent Form (Annex II) and (iii) the Data Subject Request Form (Annex III) which will be used during the implementation of the project's activities to ensure compliance with relevant applicable EU and national regulation(s).

2. DATA SUMMARY

To achieve its objectives, SUSTRACK needs to collect, generate and re-use data categorised as non-sensitive (not part of any special categories² of personal data within the General Data Protection regulation (GDPR³). This chapter of the SUSTRACK DMP defines the purpose, together with the types and formats of the data collected and generated during the implementation of the SUSTRACK project. Moreover, the description of the data origins and expected size will be provided, concluding with the data utility and potential stakeholders re-using the data.

² Special categories of personal data according to Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament (General Data Protection Regulation) include personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation.

³ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European parliament and of the council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32016R0679>.

2.1 Purpose of data collection/generation and its relation to the project objectives

The purpose of this data collection is to help achieve the successful fulfilment of the main objectives of the SUSTRACK project, with specific actions requiring data collection and generation:

1. **Gap analysis.** A desk analysis will be conducted with a specific focus on the selected case studies. The analysis will aim at reviewing the main findings from the existing literature and recent EU surveys on trends with respect to the environmental, economic and social limits of the linear, carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy.
2. **Multi-stakeholder consultation** and validation of the limits of the linear, carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy. Findings will be discussed and validated during a co-creation focus group with 15 Quadruple Helix stakeholders. The preliminary results and 20 interviews with experts will be incorporated into a survey to consolidate the findings. The AHP and ANP methods will then be used to produce a list of priorities and interdependencies based on expert judgements and consensus at online workshops/meetings involving at least 10 participants.
3. **Review of knowledge** to monitor and assess the benefits of the transition to circular, bio-based systems. Existing knowledge (in terms of indicators, data, methods and models) that addresses circularity and sustainability aspects at different levels, will be reviewed and research gaps will be identified.
4. **Improving knowledge for assessing specific aspects of the sustainable transition.** Further desk research to address critical (research) gaps and develop knowledge and recommendations on how to fill those gaps.
5. **Selection and definition of case studies from four critical sectors and case study analysis.** Cases will be selected from four sectors that have been identified as facing critical challenges within the current linear system: (a) the construction sector; (b) the textile sector; (c) the (fine) chemical sector and (d) the plastic sector.
6. **Analysis of findings and derivation of main conclusions and recommendations.** The results of the case studies will be generalised to provide conclusions and recommendations for the four bio-based sectors.
7. **Development and calibration of the Green Economy Model.** Data required for the parameterization and calibration of the Green Economy Model will be sourced from various databases. The simulations generated will serve for the analysis of cross-sectoral impacts of the transition scenarios and provide insight into the systemic impact of policies
8. **Development of policy portfolio scenarios** will formulate scenarios as a primary input for the simulations, that will define the final input requirements. The data sources include official statistics, policy documents, scientific papers and further literature in the context of bioeconomy at the national and EU level. A workshop with stakeholders will be utilized to present and verify the scenarios.

9. **Model simulation and validation of the results.** A variety of scenarios will be simulated, considering the implementation of sectoral targets both in isolation and in conjunction with others.
10. **Capacity building for local stakeholders.** Stakeholders at the national and regional levels involved in the four case studies will be empowered through at least one capacity-building seminar and support the analysis of potential pitfalls and opportunities of policy instruments for the implementation of potential transition paths, based on their contextual specificities.
11. **Identification of policy priorities.** Based on the literature review, first, a revision of policy-related opportunities and barriers for the sustainable transition will take place and with it the identification of policy priorities. These will be validated in co-creation workshops during the INSPIRE, DESIGN, IMPLEMENT and DEPLOY conferences, framing them within the context of the four selected sectors. Finally, a prioritisation survey with an expected response quota of 200 will be applied.
12. **Policy recommendations for a sustainable transition to a circular bio-based economy.** A set of recommendations will be provided based on the identified policy priorities, results of the model simulation and policy instruments of importance for sectorial stakeholders derived from the co-creation workshops. The recommendations will include indications of pressing actions (roadmap) and sustainability considerations for a sustainable transition at the national and EU level. Preliminary validation of proposed recommendations will be discussed with stakeholders during the IMPLEMENT and DEPLOY conferences.
13. **Setting up and Operation of SUSTRACK's Advisory Board.** The representatives of the stakeholder community of contributors, multipliers and adopters will constitute the advisory board.
14. **Stakeholder Engagement activities, workshops and conferences.** These will connect stakeholder feedback with the project results through engagement activities, considering all perspectives.
15. **Monitoring and assessment of Communication, Dissemination activities of SUSTRACK** with a view to measuring their results and impact, fine-tuning SUSTRACK's Dissemination and Communication Plan, as well as fulfilling the project's reporting requirements towards the Commission.
16. **Collaboration with Related Networks and Initiatives** to benefit from synergies with other relevant EU initiatives and to establish close collaboration with the project. Concluded projects: STAR-ProBio, STAR4BBI, BIOMONITOR Ongoing projects: BIOTRANSFORM, STAR4BBS, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, 3-CO, HARMONITOR, CALIMERO, ALIGNED, BIORECER and European Bioeconomy Network.

2.2 Types and formats of collected/generated data

SUSTRACK has set out to collect/generate data of various structures and formats. Along these lines, the data definition process used for this DMP is based on the source and the physical format

of the data⁴. In particular, we define two main aspects: (i) the process under which the underlying data are created/captured which includes electronic texts documents, spreadsheets, questionnaires and transcripts, among others and (ii) the storage format of quantitative and qualitative data. Examples of this aspect include easily accessible formats, such as post scripts (e.g. pdf, xps, etc.), machine-readable formats (xml, html, etc.), spreadsheets, (e.g. xls, csv, etc.), text documents (e.g. docx, rtf, etc.), compressed formats (e.g. rar, zip, etc.) or any other format required by the objectives and methodology of the activity within the framework of which is produced.

Under this framework, special attention will be paid to using open formats⁵ (such as csv, pdf, zip, etc.) and/or machine-readable formats⁶ (such as xml, json, csv, rdf, etc.) when possible, to enhance the interoperability and re-use of data. In doing so, we will be providing data that is easily readable and freely usable in any software program employed by third-parties interested in utilizing the data.

The type and formats of the data collected/generated in the context of SUSTRACK can be divided into 4 categories, namely (i) data collected/generated by direct input methods, (ii) data collected/generated from dissemination, communication, clustering and exploitation activities, (iii) data collected/generated from project management and coordination, (iv) data collected/generated from the development and use of the Green Economy Model as described in the following subsections.

2.2.1 Data collected/generated through direct input methods

Direct input methods, under the scope of SUSTRACK, involve methodologies for collecting data through desk research and interactions between consortium partners and external stakeholders, with the latter providing data to the former. Along these lines, external stakeholders undertake the role of a data subject which is a natural person whose personal data is being processed⁷. In particular, the identification and selection of suitable data subjects are based on purposeful sampling according to which, internal and external stakeholders are identified and selected by consortium partners. This is based on their role regarding the finetuning the SUSTRACK approach through localised validation activities and co-create policy recommendations (i.e., policy makers, business leaders, authorities, action groups, civil society, NGOs, etc.) and the objectives of the respective activity for which data is collected. In this context, quantitative and qualitative data will be collected/generated during SUSTRACK:

- **Quantitative data** is numerical and acquired through counting or measuring⁸. Examples of quantitative data are the yearly turnovers of a business, the hourly compensation of a

⁴ Jakobsson, U., Braukmann, R., Lundgren M., Expert Tour Guide on Data Management. Retrieved from <https://www.cessda.eu/Research-Infrastructure/Training/Expert-Tour-Guide-on-Data-Management/1.-Plan>.

⁵ According to the [Open Data Handbook](#): "An open format is a file format with no restrictions, monetary or otherwise, placed upon its use and can be fully processed with at least one free/open-source software tool and it is not encumbered by any copyrights, patents, trademarks or other restrictions so that anyone may use it".

⁶ According to the [Open Data Handbook](#): "Machine readable formats are file formats that can be automatically read and processed by a computer. Machine-readable data must be structured data".

⁷ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European parliament and of the council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32016R0679>.

⁸ Neuman, W. L. (2014). Social research methods: Qualitative and quantitative approaches. Boston: Pearson.

worker, the number of SMEs in Europe, etc. This data may be represented by ordinal, interval or ratio scales and lend themselves to statistical manipulation.

- **Qualitative data**, sometimes referred to as categorical data, is data that can be arranged into categories based on physical traits, gender, colours or anything that does not have a number associated with it⁹. Moreover, written documents, interviews, and various forms of in-field observation are all sources of qualitative data. Examples of qualitative data are the preferences of learning, skillsets, country of origin, etc.

Additional details with respect to the different types and formats of data that will be collected through direct input methods under the frame of SUSTRACK are provided below.

1. **Gap analysis.** A desk analysis will be conducted by UNIT to extract the main findings from the existing literature (T1.1). This will involve a review of high-quality scientific articles in high-impact academic journals and well-known databases of peer-reviewed literature (e.g., Web of Science, Science Direct), as well as renowned and influential studies and reports published in the grey literature (e.g., government and industry reports, reports and deliverables of related projects). Information will also be retrieved from active EU projects (e.g., STAR4BBS, BIORECER, BRANCHES, TRANSITION2BIO, GENB, BIOGOV.NET), the EC Knowledge Centre and recent EU surveys on trends in limits of the linear, carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy. The data collected will be mainly **qualitative** in nature with descriptive texts and then they will be deposited and analysed in excel spreadsheets (.xlsx). After the analysis, the gathered information will be used to prepare a text document (.docx and .pdf) as D1.1 (M6).
2. **Multi-stakeholder consultation and validation of the limits of the linear, carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy.** For identifying and consolidating the challenges faced by the linear, fossil-based economy, related to environmental, economic and social sustainability aspects, as well as technical, structural and cultural barriers, different stakeholder activities will be implemented. First of all, findings obtained in the previous task will be discussed and validated during a co-creation focus group (organised by PEDAL) with 15 Quadruple Helix (i.e., policy makers, industry professionals, researchers, NGOs, citizens) stakeholders from Europe, selected with the help of all partners (M8). The workshop will be organized in the framework of the official EU Green Week 2023. Data generated during the event (e.g. minutes) will be saved in the project repository. In addition, 20 interviews with experts (from at least 6 MSs) will be incorporated into a survey (in English, sent to more than 400 stakeholders across the EU) to consolidate the findings (M11). The results will be shared during the INSPIRE conference (M12). For each interview, a short summary will be prepared and shared with the interviewed experts. In addition, the questionnaire and the results of the survey will be saved in the project repository. Based on the results, reports will be created.
3. **Review of knowledge to monitor and assess the benefits of the transition to circular, bio-based systems.** A desk analysis will be led by TEC to identify research gaps in existing practice (T2.1). This will involve a review of scientific articles, as well as studies and reports published in the grey literature (e.g., government and industry reports, reports and deliverables of related projects). Information will also be retrieved from past and active EU projects (e.g., BIOMONITOR, STAR4BBS, BIORECER etc.), the EC Knowledge Centre. The data collected will concern the type of indicators, data and methods currently used to assess and monitor bioeconomy. These will be mainly qualitative in nature with descriptive

⁹ Neuman, W. L. (2014). Social research methods: Qualitative and quantitative approaches. Boston: Pearson.

texts and then they will be deposited and analysed in excel spreadsheets (.xlsx). After the analysis, the gathered information will be used to prepare a text document (.docx and .pdf) as D2.1 (M10).

4. **Improving knowledge for assessing specific aspects of the sustainable transition.** This involves a review of scientific articles, as well as studies and reports published in the grey literature (e.g., government and industry reports, reports and deliverables of related projects), but also information gathering through interviews with stakeholders in the 4 case studies. So the information collected will be both qualitative and quantitative in nature and will be deposited and analysed in excel spreadsheets (.xlsx). After the analysis, the gathered information will be used to prepare two public documents (.docx and .pdf) as D2.2 (M20) and D2.3 (M32).
5. **Development of a framework to monitor and assess the benefits of the sustainable transition, including a dashboard for stakeholders.** This will be based on outputs from T2.1 and T2.2 and from WP3 and WP4 and will consist of a text document (.docx and .pdf) (D2.4 (M36)).
6. **Selection and definition of case studies from four critical sectors and case study analysis.** BAM is coordinating the selection of case studies to be used during the implementation of the SUSTRACK project. In total 15 case studies have been shortlisted and for each of them, a fact sheet is being prepared. They will be included as public documents (.docx and .pdf) in D3.1 (M6).
7. **Analysis of findings and derivation of main conclusions and recommendations.** This refers specifically to T3.3 (Case study analysis) and T3.4 (Analysis of finding and main conclusions) which both focus on the case study work. The case study work will be used to improve the indicator set and assessment methodologies (from WP2), provide guidance on pathways for changing and defining potential (policy) intervention options (related to WP4 modelling the future and WP5, best policy instruments involved). So all this case study work will generate a lot of knowledge in the form of qualitative data, outcomes of stakeholder exchanges in workshops, both qualitative and quantitative data and PowerPoints with guidance to lead discussions and support the exchange of information. All which will generate a lot of data and insights (included in working documents in .word and .xls format) which will all be systematically reported in two deliverables (reports .word and .pdf format). In D3.3 (M28) all case study assessment results are reported per case study and. In D3.4 Overall findings, recommendations and conclusions from the specific case studies and more overall over the case studies are presented (M30) again in the form of a .word/.pdf document.
8. **Development of policy portfolio scenarios** The policy instruments and set measures will be collected by all case study responsible, work package partners and further experts, using a template in an excel file. The descriptive part of the scenarios will be presented as .docx/.pdf files. For the Workshop presentation a PowerPoint file (.ppt) will be prepared.
9. **Capacity building for local stakeholders.** This task includes making accessible and usable for external stakeholders the materials and tools prepared in different stages of the project by the project partners in charge of their development. This may include the publication of online tools on the SUSTRACK webpage (e.g. Monitoring dashboard as the outcome of T2.3), as well as the accompanying documentation that explains its use in text documents (.docx and .pdf). Guidelines for the identification and review of case study information

(T3.2) as well as the conclusions and recommendation to the bio-based sectors (T3.4) will be translated into user-friendly formats, according to the identified target groups of each of them, which will include text documents and presentations (.docx, .pdf and .pptx). Finally, the capacity-building materials prepared in publishable formats (.pdf) and model tutorials (.pptx) will be utilized in online webinars, allowing for a recording of the data produced (e.g. .mp4, .mpeg, .wmv).

10. **Identification of policy priorities.** This refers specifically to T5.1 in which policy priorities are identified to support the sustainable transition by reviewing the limits of the linear, fossil-based and carbon-intensive economy (WP1), as well as policy-related opportunities and barriers for the sustainable transition. This will involve a systematic review of scientific and grey literature and especially results of former EU H2020 and BBI projects: e.g., BERST, S2BIOM, Power4Bio, Celebio, STAR-ProBio, STAR4BBI. Also, national policy data is to be collected in the 4 case studies of the project. All this information will be collected in excel (.xls) files and summarized in reports (.docx). The derived policy priorities and examples of good policies will be validated in the policy co-creation workshops that will take place at the INSPIRE, DESIGN, IMPLEMENT and DEPLOY conferences. This will generate PowerPoint presentations (.ppt). It will also lead to information collected through polls during the workshop (anonymous information) and workshop summary reports, which will also be included in the Sustrack deliverable reports (D5.1 and D5.2) as annexes. Finally, an additional prioritisation survey is planned in order to increase the number of stakeholders consulted to more than 200. Furthermore, this information will be handled following privacy legislation and all information will only be summarized in D5.1 in the form of tables in which answers can never be traced back to individuals. The format to process the survey data is going to build as an Excel file (.xls). This information will not be published, but only used for internal project purposes.
11. **Policy recommendations for a sustainable transition towards a circular bio-based economy.** This activity will be based on the resulting data from WP1, WP3, WP4 and T5.1, in consideration of policies status-quo at the EU level and for the selected sectors and countries where the case studies are placed. Also, the data generated during the stakeholder engagement activities (e.g, co-creation workshops and from T5.2), which have a qualitative nature, will be utilized for this activity. The consolidation of collected information, in order to point out policy priorities at the sectorial level and provide recommendations and guidelines to policymakers, will be prepared in documents (.docx and .pdf) as well as presentation formats (e.g. .pptx).
12. **Setting up and Operation of SUSTRACK's Advisory Board (AB).** The data regarding the setup of the SUSTRACK AB fall under Task 6.2 (PC) and include personal information of candidate AB members (e.g., name and surname, gender, organisation, position, email, country of placement, and a brief description of the professional profile). They will be collected by the consortium partners, under the guidance of PC, following the process of retrieving information from online public sources (professional websites, etc). Each partner will be asked to identify at least 2 suitable relevant stakeholders from their own network and provide to the consortium information that is publicly available. The candidates will be assessed by a selection process and will be formally approached and invited to give their consent to become members of the AB. The data will be stored in text documents, image and spreadsheet format (.docx, .xlsx, .pdf, .jpeg).
13. **Stakeholder Engagement activities, co-creation workshops and conferences.** This section refers to data that will be collected through stakeholder activities and events, conducted in the context of SUSTRACK, with the aim to connect stakeholder feedback with

the project results. The data will be collected in two levels, the first one will be the EU-wide survey and interviews with EU citizens which will be implemented by BAM and PEDAL and shared through the INSPIRE, DESIGN and IMPLEMENT conferences. The second level will be regional surveys and interviews with local actors facilitated by the partners through the DEPLOY conferences. The data will be stored in text documents, image and spreadsheet format (.docx, .xlsx, .pdf, .jpeg).

The Co-Creation Workshops are anticipated to engage a set of selected stakeholders from industry, government and project partners, to identify policy priorities, define corresponding policy actions and provide recommendations to policy makers in support of the sustainable transition. The respective discussions, ideas, and relevant feedback are expected to be fully utilised and written up by means of notes and the elaboration of guidelines for customization purposes in text documents (e.g. .docx).

14. **Collaboration with Related Networks and Initiatives** to benefit from synergies with other relevant EU initiatives and to establish close collaboration with other projects. The data regarding collaboration with Related Networks and Initiatives fall under Task 6.3 (FVA), will be reported under D6.2 and D6.4 (FVA) and include information on projects and initiatives and their key contacts (e.g. Project's Year, Call identifier, Call topic, Acronym, Coordinator, Cordis/website ID, Full title, Key Contact information, EuBioNet Membership). Data will be collected by FVA through direct access to databases generated in previous projects. In particular, FVA EuBioNet and FVA contacts in the bioeconomy sector databases will be used for the project's activities by FVA, but will not be shared among partners or be subject to further exploitation by the consortium. Stakeholders gave consent to involve them in other related projects. The data will be stored in text documents (.docx or .pdf files), spreadsheet format (.xlsx, .csv files), presentations (.ppt files), audio-visual files (.mp4 files), and images (.jpeg or .png files).

Data collected/generated through direct input methods will be stored in standard .docx as well as .xlsx formats. These formats allow the documentation of information from various files and documents in a single location. By doing so, it is possible to circulate raw data from transcripts, as well as text, images and other objects from other files to one document file or multiple tabs of a single spreadsheet. Moreover, both formats can be immediately converted into open and machine-readable formats (e.g. .xml and .csv) boosting the interoperability and re-usability of the data produced in the framework of SUSTRACK.

2.2.2 Data collected/generated from dissemination, communication, stakeholder engagement and exploitation activities

The data deriving by monitoring and assessment of the dissemination and communication results of the project and by the clustering and exploitation with a view to measuring the impact of the relevant activities, fall under WP6 (FVA and PC) and include (i). Website and social media accounts (i.e., YouTube, LinkedIn, Twitter) analytics; (ii). Data collected from project events; (iii) Data collected from dissemination and communication actions (e.g., participation in external events, participation in project workshops, etc.); (iii). Newsletter subscriptions and (iv) Exploitation of project results. The data will be identified through online analytics, utilising social media accounts, partners reporting etc. FVA is responsible for sending the necessary templates (.docx, .xlsx) to all partners, alongside guidelines on how to fill them in, as well as for collecting input on an *ad-hoc* basis (i.e., each time a dissemination or stakeholder engagement action is performed). FVA is also responsible for preparing the necessary reports to evaluate the overall progress of dissemination and communication activities (measuring outcomes against pre-set KPIs) throughout

the lifespan of the project. The storage format of the data to be collected during the project's duration, includes .csv, .docx, .xlsx, .pdf, .pptx, .mp4, .jpeg and .png files. Machine readable formats have priority over MS Office file formats if available.

2.2.2.1 Website and social media analytics

Website analytics:

Social media statistics (YouTube, Twitter and LinkedIn): These data will be collected/generated through periodic monitoring of the project's social media statistics (i.e. YouTube, Twitter and LinkedIn) with a view to measuring and assessing the performance and results of the project's social media activity in terms of dissemination and communication. With that in mind, the data will be mostly quantitative in nature addressing the metrics reached on each channel (e.g., number of followers, tweets impressions on Twitter, number of people reached through LinkedIn posts, etc.). Additionally, these data will be followed by an analysis of the results stemming from them and possible ways to improve the results so as to reach the project's targets. All in all, the data will be stored in a Microsoft excel file (.xlsx and other machine readable formats) while at the same time, the analysis of the results will be stored in a standard word document (.docx and other machine readable formats).

2.2.2.2 Data collected from project events and stakeholder engagement activities

These data will be collected during the implementation of the project through: (i) the different events (e.g. co-creation workshops, validation workshops, conferences, interviews, physical and virtual events, etc.) organised by SUSTRACK (either alone or jointly with other projects or initiatives) consisting of the participants' lists that will enclose demographic information about the participants; and (ii) the participation of SUSTRACK partners in relevant third party events in order to reach out and engage stakeholders, thus collecting general information about the events attended and their outreach.

Along these lines, these data will be collected so as to keep track of the results of activities in events for stakeholder engagement and provide the opportunity to project partners to report on these activities. Moreover, these data will be updated every time a partner attends an event, or a partner organises an event. Finally, the data will be both quantitative and qualitative in nature and will be stored in a standard spreadsheet (.xlsx, .csv, .json, .xml).

2.2.2.3 Data collected from dissemination and communication actions

These data will be collected through the periodic monitoring of the project's miscellaneous dissemination activities such as publications in relevant journals, posts in blogs, etc. The data will consist of an excel form designed to keep track of any kind of communication and dissemination activity, including, but not limited to, press releases, social media posts, website articles, interviews, events (conferences, meetings, workshops, etc.), other publications, e-mails, presentations, informal discussions, seminars, etc. The purpose of collecting these data is to assess the outreach and efficiency of the dissemination activities during the implementation of the project. For this purpose, a template will be shared with all partners to recommend activities to be performed and log the activities they performed. The template is provided also online so that the partners can directly update their input. Finally, all the data will be integrated into a single excel file (.xlsx).

2.2.2.4 Newsletter subscriptions

A subscription form hosted on the project's website will aid the collection of these data in which any interested stakeholder can freely provide their contact details in a dedicated sign-up form so as to receive the most up-to-date news and outcomes of the project. A newsletter will be sent to subscribers once per 12 months. With that in mind, these data will be collected so that interested stakeholders can be informed about SUSTRACK's progress and upcoming events. The data will be comprised of a list of subscribers along with their personal information such as: (i) email address, (ii) first and last name, (iii) country, (iv) type of organisation, (v) region and (vi) gender. A copy of this contact list will be stored to a dedicated cloud server BlueiTech (<https://blueitech.com/>), which is used for e-mail campaigns and newsletters distribution. All personal information included in this contact list will be used and protected according to BlueiTech's Privacy Policy. Subscribers can find details about how their personal information is managed on the respective privacy policy section of the SUSTRACK website.

2.2.3 Data collected/generated from project management and coordination

During the implementation phase of SUSTRACK, data will be collected from management and coordination activities. More specifically, the collection/generation of data comes up from partners' communication, Quality Assurance processes, progress monitoring, risk analysis, workshops and events. The above data series are expected to be both qualitative and quantitative in nature and will be stored in various types of formats, such as captured photographs, noted minutes, written insights in text documents, reports presenting outcomes and progress of activities, and participant lists. The storage format of the data to be collected during the project's duration, includes preferably machine-readable format such as .csv, alternatively .docx, .xlsx, .pdf, .ppt, .jpeg and .png files.

2.2.4 Data collected/generated from the development and use of the Green Economy Model

The development and calibration of the simulation model require sourcing data for socioeconomic and environmental key indicators included in the Green Economy Model. The World Bank Data Portal and EUROSTAT will serve as main data sources for macroeconomic indicators (e.g. GDP total and by sector, employment, System of National Accounts, etc.) and data gaps as well as forecasts on economic performance will be supplemented using the World Economic Outlook database of the International Monetary Fund. For the calibration of country-specific indicators for which no data is available in the aforementioned data sources, the public database of national statistics offices may be consulted. The data used for parameter development as well as the validation of simulation results will be stored in excel spreadsheets (.xls; .xlsx; .csv format). The implementation of additional causal connections that are not yet included in the Green Economy Model may require the review of scientific articles, reports or studies, typically in .pdf format.

At the same time, the Green Economy Model will be used to simulate baseline and transition scenarios and hence generate additional data used to perform the analysis of policy impacts. The outputs from the Green Economy model will be exported from the modelling software (Vensim) and stored in excel spreadsheets (.xlsx format) for further processing. Additional visual materials developed using Vensim may be provided in .jpeg or .tiff format.

2.3 Origin of data and re-use of pre-existing data

In the context of SUSTRACK, new data will be collected/generated by partners as well as external stakeholders participating in the activities of the project. With that in mind and aside from consortium partners, external groups of stakeholders from which new data will originate include:

- Business community
- Authorities
- Policy makers at regional, national and EU levels
- Civil society
- Researchers and academic experts
- All Others

Moreover, pre-existing data will be utilised within the context of SUSTRACK as well. In particular, outputs from EU-funded projects (e.g., STAR-ProBio, STAR4BBI, BIOMONITOR, SUSTRACK, BIOTRNSFORM, STAR4BBS, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, 3-CO, HARMONITOR, CALIMERO, ALIGNED, BIORECER etc.), national projects and other relevant initiatives to a large extent will provide a solid basis for SUSTRACK. The SUSTRACK consortium will strive to make the most of and advance the work and results of these projects. Finally, consortium partners' internal knowledge, experience and expertise from their participation in other projects and initiatives will, directly and indirectly, support the implementation of activities throughout the project.

2.4 Expected size of data

The table that follows presents the different activities implemented during the course of the project in which data is collected/generated, the types and formats of the data as well as the expected size of the data.

Table 1: Expected size of data

No	Name of activity	Data	Type of data	Format of data	Expected size of data (KB)*
1	Gap analysis	The literature gaps and trade-offs	Notes, spreadsheets	.docx .xlsx	500 KB
2	Multi-stakeholder consultation and validation of the limits of the linear, carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy	Literature review, interviews, stakeholder event, survey.	Notes, spreadsheets	.docx .xlsx	500 KB
3	Review of knowledge to monitor and assess the benefits of the transition to circular, bio-based systems	Knowledge gaps related to indicators, data, methods and models used to monitor and assess bioeconomy.	Notes, spreadsheets	.docx .xlsx	500 KB
4	Improving knowledge for assessing specific aspects of the sustainable transition	Description of data needs and best methodologies on indicators for monitoring specific aspects of the sustainability transition in the case studies	Notes, spreadsheets, reports	.docx .xlsx	40 MB
5	Development of a framework	Data on indicators, data,	Notes,	.docx	500 KB

	to monitor and assess the benefits of the sustainable transition, including a dashboard for stakeholders	methods and models used to monitor and assess bioeconomy	spreadsheets	.xlsx	
6	Selection and definition of case studies from four critical sectors and case study analysis	Report on selection steps and final selection including fact sheets on short listed case studies. Also excels with long and short lists of potential case study candidates.	Notes, spreadsheets, reports	.docx .xlsx	10 MB
7	Analysis of findings and derivation of main conclusions and recommendations	Two reports with separate chapters per case study, reports on outcomes of workshops and several excel files with collected data, knowledge in a predefined structure	Notes, spreadsheets, reports	.docx .xlsx	80 MB
8	Development of policy portfolio scenarios will formulate scenarios as a primary input for the simulations, that will define the final input requirements	List of policy instruments and related case sector specific goals (e.g. amount of CO2 reduction, energy reduction, efficiency increase), Scenario description, Presentation in the Workshops	Spreadsheet, report, Presentation	.csv .docx pptx.	500KB
9	Model simulation and validation of the results	Output of macroeconomic, social and environmental key indicators, such as GDP, emissions, energy demand, employment and more	Spreadsheets, potentially diagrams, report.	.xlsx .docx	Size of output data is approx. 10-20MB Size of report approx. 10-15MB
10	The development and calibration of the simulation model	System of National Accounts, macroeconomic data (population, employment, GDP, etc.), land use data, final energy consumption, power generation, GHG emissions, relevant statistics on bioeconomy sectors, scenario	Spreadsheet	.xlsx	Input data: approx. 15-20MB
11	Capacity building for local stakeholders	Presentations, documentation of SUSTRACK tools/methods, capacity building materials from the model simulation, guidance for utilisation of all materials.	Text documents, presentations, recording videos.	.docx .pdf .pptx .mp4 (or similar)	500 KB
12	Identification of policy priorities	Data in literature and EU2020 at policy level.	Text documents	.docx	2-10MB

			, presentations	.pdf .pptx	
13	Policy recommendations for a sustainable transition towards a circular bio-based economy	data on prioritized policy actions at EU and CS level, presentations	Text documents, presentations	.docx .pdf .pptx	2-10 MB
14	Setting up and Operation of SUSTRACK's Advisory Board	Information of candidate AB members (e.g., name and surname, mail, brief description of professional profile)	Notes, spreadsheets, images	.docx, .xlsx, .pdf, .jpeg	500 KB
15	Stakeholder Engagement activities, workshops and conferences	Photos, number of event participants, presentations, interviews, surveys, Direct data input by users by newsletter subscription	Notes, spreadsheets, images, presentations	.docx, .xlsx, .pdf, .ppt, .jpeg, .png	1000 KB
16	Monitoring and assessment of Communication, Dissemination activities	Website and social media analytics, Data collected from project events, Newsletter subscriptions, Data collected from dissemination and communication activities/actions	Text document spreadsheets, presentations, audio-visual files, images	.docx .pdf .xlsx .csv .ppt .mp4 .jpeg .png	1000 KB
* The estimated expected size of the data is based on the adjusted size of data generated via similar activities of project partners in the past unless otherwise indicated.					

2.5 Data utility

The stakeholders that may find meaningful utility for the data to be collected/generated by the project (both within as well as outside of SUSTRACK's consortium) along with the benefits that could arise for them by utilizing these data, are concisely presented in the table that follows.

Table 2: Data utility

Stakeholder group	Data utility
Policy makers	SUSTRACK aims at supporting policy makers in their efforts to develop sustainable pathways to replace fossil-based, carbon-intensive systems with circular, bio-based systems at EU and regional scales. More specifically the project's generated data and results will provide guidelines and policy recommendations as well as identification of policy priorities. Along these lines, data generated may be of great utility for experts who design, implement and/or fund relevant policies.
Industrial ecosystem	The data created/generated through SUSTRACK will provide insights on how to accomplish networking and stakeholder

	engagement to build the connections required to accelerate bio-based innovation. The results of the project are expected (i) to increase awareness regarding bio-based systems and their benefits and (ii) to provide useful feedback on a policy making level regarding integrating bio-based value chain development into broader policies and regional development plans. To this end, data generated through SUSTRACK may be of great utility for industry advisors and investors engaging in the implementation and funding of relevant policies.
Scientific community	In the frame of the SUSTRACK project, interdisciplinary research is performed that largely builds upon prior research efforts to generate insights on the transition from linear fossil-based systems to circular and bio-based systems across Europe. Additionally, local stakeholders are engaged in the project's co-creation, mutual learning, and validation activities in identifying environmental, economic and social limits of a linear carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy and improving existing assessment methodologies. Research data of the project that will be published in reports or peer-reviewed scientific journals as well as deposited in open repositories can be of great utility for scientists in the field, aggregating and classifying existing scientific knowledge and creating new knowledge and empirical open data on the transition to circular and bio-based systems.
Civil society	SUSTRACK aims to engage local stakeholders in its activities in order to make sure that their perspective is taken into consideration in the development of regional policies.
Project partners	The data collected/generated during SUSTRACK is the cornerstone for project partners in order to produce evidence-based results and ultimately achieve the objectives of the project. Indeed, these data enable the co-creation and validation of findings that will assist in embedding policy priorities in regional and European agendas. At the same time, this data may be meaningful for project partners beyond the end of the project as well, enabling them to build and capitalise upon interesting ideas and opportunities that may emerge to ensure the long-term sustainability of the SUSTRACK results.

3. FAIR DATA

The guidelines on Data Management Plans available in the [Horizon Europe Data Management Plan Template](#) of the Commission emphasise the importance of making the data produced by projects funded under Horizon Europe **Findable, Accessible, Interoperable as well as Reusable (FAIR)**, with a view to ensuring its sound management. This means using standards and metadata to make data discoverable, specifying data sharing procedures and which data will be open, allowing data exchange via open repositories as well as facilitating the reusability of the data. With that in mind, the following sections of the DMP lay out the methodology followed in the framework of SUSTRACK with respect to making data findable, accessible and interoperable as well as ensuring their preservation and open access, with a view to increasing its re-use.

3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1. Data discoverability and identification mechanism

SUSTRACK places special emphasis on enhancing the discoverability of the data collected/generated during the course of its activities. To this end, the project follows a metadata-driven approach so as to increase the searchability of the data, while also facilitating their understanding and re-use. Metadata is defined as “data about data” or “information about information”¹⁰. It is usually structured textual information that describes something about the creation, content, or context of a digital resource - be it a single file, part of a single file, or a collection of many files. Metadata is the glue which links information and data across the world wide web. It is the tool that helps people to discover, manage, describe, preserve and build relationships with and between digital resources¹¹.

In particular, three distinct types of metadata exist¹², as presented below:

- **Descriptive metadata** is used to identify and describe collections and related information resources. Descriptive metadata at the local level helps with searching and retrieving. In an online environment, descriptive metadata helps to discover resources. Most of the time, it includes information such as the title, author, date, description, identifier, etc.
- **Administrative metadata** is used to facilitate the management of information resources. It is helpful for both short-term and long-term management and processing of data. This is information that will not usually be relevant to the public but will be essential for staff to manage collections internally. Such metadata may be location information, acquisition information, etc.
- **Structural metadata** enables the navigation and presentation of electronic resources. It documents how the components of an item are organized. Examples of structural metadata could be the way in which pages are ordered to form chapters of a book, a photograph that is included in a manuscript or a scrapbook or the JPEG and TIF files that were created from the original photograph negative, linked together.

With that in mind, **data produced/used during SUSTRACK is discoverable with metadata** suitable to its content and format. The project employs **metadata standards** to produce rich and consistent metadata with a view to supporting the long-term discovery, use and integrity of its data (see Subsection 3.1.5 for more details on the metadata standards adopted by SUSTRACK).

In parallel, to further increase data discoverability, the **data produced by SUSTRACK and deemed open for sharing and re-use will be deposited to European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) (<https://eosc-portal.eu/>), an open data repository**. The EOSC is an environment for hosting and processing research data to support EU science. The portal provides European researchers, innovators, companies and citizens with a federated and open multi-disciplinary environment where they can publish, find and re-use data, tools and services for research, innovation and educational purposes. This environment operates under well-defined conditions to ensure trust and safeguard the public interest.

¹⁰ Huxley, L., & Jacobs, N. (2004). Online information services in the Social Sciences. Oxford: Chandos.

¹¹ Foulonneau, M., & Riley, J. (2008). Metadata for digital resources: Implementation, systems design and interoperability. Oxford: Chandos.

¹² Caplan, P. (2003). Metadata fundamentals for all librarians. Chicago: American Library Association.

The EOSC enables a step change across scientific communities and research infrastructures towards

- seamless access
- FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability) management
- reliable reuse of research data and all other digital objects produced along the research life cycle (e.g. methods, software and publications)

EOSC ultimately aims to develop a Web of FAIR Data and services for science in Europe upon which a wide range of value-added services can be built. These range from visualization and analytics to long-term information preservation or the monitoring of the uptake of open science practices.

It accepts any file format, promotes peer-reviewed openly accessible research, allows the creation of own collections and it is available free of charge both for SUSTRACK to upload and share data as well as for other stakeholders to explore, download and re-use this data.

Moreover, by employing this data repository, the **data produced during the implementation of the project is locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism**. Indeed, SUSTRACK will be able to assign globally resolvable **Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)** on any data uploaded to EOSC. An identifier is a unique identification code that is applied to a dataset so that it can be unambiguously referenced¹³. For example, a catalogue number is an identifier for a particular specimen and an ISBN code is an identifier for a particular book. PIDs are simply maintainable identifiers that allow for permanent reference to a digital object. In other words, PIDs are a way of giving digital resources, such as documents, images and data records, a unique and persistent reference number.

At the same time, **datasets not uploaded to EOSC will be deposited in a searchable resource** (the cloud web storage service of the project) and utilise well-tailored identification mechanisms as well, in the form of standard naming conventions that will safeguard their consistency and make them **easily locatable** for partners within the frame of the project. The following subsection provides further details in this respect.

3.1.2. Naming conventions

Following a consistent set of naming conventions in the development of the project's data files can greatly enhance their searchability. With that in mind, SUSTRACK creates consistent data file names that provide clues to their content, status and versioning, while also increasing their discoverability. In doing so, project partners as well as interested stakeholders can easily identify a file as well as classify and sort them.

According to the UK Data Archive ([UK Data Service, 2017b](#)), a best practice in naming convention is to create brief yet meaningful names for data files, that facilitate classification. The naming convention should avoid the utilisation of spaces, dots and special characters (such as & or !), whereas the use of underscores is endorsed, to separate elements in the data file name and make them understandable. At the same time, versioning should be a part of a naming convention to clearly identify the changes and edits in a file.

¹³ Tonkin, E. Persistent identifiers: considering the options (2008), Ariadne Issue 56

With that in mind and to facilitate the reference of the datasets that will be produced during its implementation, SUSTRACK employs a **standard naming convention that integrates versioning and takes into account the possibility of creating multiple datasets** during an activity that entails data collection/generation. Indeed, SUSTRACK's naming convention considers this issue and addresses it by employing a unique element that captures the number of datasets that are produced under the same activity.

In particular, the **naming convention employed by the project is described below avoiding spaces or other special characters, using only the standard alphabet A-Z0-9.**

[Name of project] _ [Name of Study] _ [Number of dataset] _ [Issue Date] _ [Version number]

- **Name of project:** SUSTRACK
- **Name of Study:** A short version of the name of the activity for which the dataset is created.
- **Number of dataset:** An indication of the number assigned to the dataset.
- **Issue Date:** The date on which the latest version of the dataset was modified (YYYY.MM.DD.).
- **Version number:** The versioning number of a dataset.

With the above in mind, some **indicative examples** to showcase the naming structure applied in the context of SUSTRACK are provided below:

- **SUSTRACK_Casestudies_Dataset1_2023.1.30_v1** -The first dataset generated from the collection of case studies from four critical sectors. In this task, cases are selected from four sectors that have been identified as facing critical challenges within the current linear system: (a) the construction sector; (b) the textile sector; (c) the (fine) chemical; and (d) the plastic sector. This is the first version of the dataset that was last modified on the 30th of January 2023 (30/01/2023).
- **SUSTRACK_GapAnalysis_Dataset1_2023.02.15_v1** -The first dataset generated from the gap analysis after the literature review. In this task, the environmental, economic, and social limits of the linear, carbon-intensive, and fossil-based economy have been identified. This is the first version of the dataset that was last modified on the 15th of February 2023 (15/02/2023).
- **SUSTRACK_KnowledgeGaps1_2023.02.27_V1.xlsx**. -The first dataset generated from the T2.1, identifying the body of knowledge. In this task, Next, the research items will be reviewed to identify gaps. This is the first version of the dataset that was last modified on the 27th of February 2023 (27/02/2023).

3.1.3 Search keywords

The project's data will be provided with search keywords with a view to optimizing its re-use by interested stakeholders during its entire lifetime. With that in mind, the metadata standards employed by SUSTRACK provide opportunities for tagging the data collected/generated and its content with keywords. In general, keywords are a subset of metadata and include words and phrases used to name data. In the context of SUSTRACK, keywords are used to add valuable

information to the data collected/generated as well as to facilitate the description and interpretation of its content and value.

Along these lines, the project's strategy on keywords is underpinned by the following principles:

- The who, the what, the when, the where, and the why should be covered.
- Consistency among the different keyword tags needs to be ensured.
- Relevant, understandable and clear keywording ought to be sought.

In general, the keywords will comprise terms related to circular bioeconomy, governance models, and regional authorities. The keywords will accurately reflect the content of the datasets and avoid words used only once or twice within them.

3.1.4 Versioning

Versioning of information makes a revision of datasets uniquely identifiable and can be used to determine whether and how data changed over time and to define specifically which version the creators/editors are working with. Moreover, effective data versioning enables understanding if a newer version of a dataset is available and which are the changes between the different versions allowing for comparisons and preventing confusion. In this context, **a clear version number indicator is used in the naming convention** of every data file produced during SUSTRACK in order to facilitate the identification of different versions.

3.1.5 Standards for metadata creation

SUSTRACK employs standards for creating metadata for data collected/generated by the project, with a view to describing it with **rich metadata** and thus improving their discoverability and searchability. As a result, effective searching, improved digital curation and easy sharing will be realized. In addition, the metadata standards applied enable the integration of metadata from a variety of sources into other technical systems.

With that in mind, **for SUSTRACKS's openly available data, the metadata standards provided by EOSC will be used.** EOSC creates metadata to accompany the datasets that are uploaded to its repository, extending their reach to a wider audience of interested stakeholders. This metadata can be exported in several standard formats, including open and machine-readable ones (such as MARXML, Dublin Core, and DataCite Metadata Schema).

Project **data not available for re-use will also be annotated with open and machine-readable metadata** following the **Dublin Core Metadata standard**. The Dublin Core Metadata element set (certified with the ISO Standard 15836) is a standard which can be easily understood and implemented and as such, is one of the best-known metadata standards. It was originally developed as a core set of elements for describing the content of web pages and enabling their search and retrieval. Among the reasons for selecting this standard is also the fact that **EOSC is compatible with Dublin Core metadata formats** and thus any initially closed data, that may become open at a later stage (e.g., due to a change in the consortium's policy), will not lose its metadata. With that said, the Dublin Core metadata standard is a simple yet effective set for creating rich metadata that will describe a wide range of resources. The fifteen-element "Dublin Core" described in this standard is part of a larger set of metadata vocabularies and technical specifications maintained by the [Dublin Core Metadata Initiative \(DCMI\)](#). The full set of vocabularies, also includes sets of resource classes, vocabulary encoding schemes, and syntax

encoding schemes. An online metadata generator will be used to produce the different metadata elements required (dublincoregenerator.com).

3.2 Making data accessible

3.2.1 Openly available and closed data

SUSTRACK follows the guidelines of the [Horizon Europe Data Management Plan Template](#), and is in line with FAIR principles and the rule “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”, aiming to “make the data collected/generated openly available with as few restrictions as possible, while at the same time protecting sensitive data from inappropriate access”¹⁴. This calls project partners to disseminate the project’s data that have the potential to offer long-term value to external stakeholders and do not harm the confidentiality and privacy of the stakeholders that contributed to the collection/generation of this data, maximising the beneficial impact of SUSTRACK.

Only anonymised and aggregated data will be made open to ensure that data subjects cannot be identified in any reports, publications and/or datasets resulting from the project. The relevant project partner in each case will **undertake all the necessary anonymisation procedures** to anonymise the data in such a way that the data subject is no longer identifiable (more details on data management responsibilities are provided in Chapter 5.).

To this end, it is important to keep in mind that during the process of data anonymisation, data identifiers need to be removed, generalised, aggregated or distorted. Moreover, **anonymisation is different from pseudonymisation**, which falls under a distinct category in the GDPR. Anonymisation theoretically destroys any way of identifying the data subject, while pseudonymisation allows for the data subject to be re-identified with additional information. Along these lines, the table which follows provides a **list of good practices** for the anonymisation of quantitative and qualitative data derived from the tour guide on data management of the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA).

*Table 3: Good practices for data anonymisation**

Type of data	Good practices
Quantitative data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Remove or aggregate variables or reduce the precision or detailed textual meaning of a variable. Aggregate or reduce the precision of a variable such as age or place of residence. As a general rule, report the lowest level of geo-referencing that will not potentially breach respondent confidentiality. Generalise the meaning of a detailed text variable by replacing potentially disclosive free-text responses with more general text. Restrict the upper or lower ranges of a continuous variable to hide outliers if the values for certain individuals are unusual or atypical within the wider group researched.
Qualitative data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use pseudonyms or generic descriptors to edit identifying information, rather than blanking-out that information.

¹⁴ Koulocheri, E. (2017). What is the Open Research Data Pilot? Retrieved from <https://www.openaire.eu/what-is-the-open-research-data-pilot>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plan anonymisation at the time of transcription or initial write-up, (longitudinal studies may be an exception if relationships between waves of interviews need special attention for harmonised editing). • Use pseudonyms or replacements that are consistent within the research team and throughout the project. For example, using the same pseudonyms in publications and follow-up research. • Use 'search and replace' techniques carefully so that unintended changes are not made, and misspelt words are not missed. • Identify replacements in the text clearly, for example with [brackets] or using XML tags such as <seg> word to be anonymised</seg>. <p>Create an anonymisation log (also known as a de-anonymisation key) of all replacements, aggregations or removals made and store such a log securely and separately from the anonymised data files.</p>
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*Source: Tour guide on data management of the CESSDA¹⁵

With that in mind, the following table presents the data collected/generated during the course of the project that will be made openly available. In case certain data cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), a justification for that choice is provided.

It is important to note that all personal data collected/generated will be considered closed data prior to their anonymisation and aggregation to safeguard the confidentiality of the data subjects.

3.2.2 Data accessibility and availability

Public access to the open data will be made available through EOSC. The data will be fully accessible thanks to the included metadata and the search facility available on EOSC. At the same time, closed data are intended to be stored and shared amongst authorised members of the consortium through cloud storage and file-sharing providers which constitute structures that maintain and manage data and make these data accessible over a network, usually the internet (i.e. Google Drive). Before starting using these cloud services from providers situated both inside and outside the EEA we have ensured that they comply with the relevant GDPR requirements.

The following table (Table 4) presents where data will be made accessible in the context of SUSTRACK.

Table 4: Data accessibility

No	Data	Accessibility
1	Gap analysis	The results will be shared in D1.1 which is a public report.
2	Multi-stakeholder consultation and validation of the limits of the linear, carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy	The results will be shared in D1.2 which is a public report
3	Review of knowledge to monitor and assess the benefits of the transition to circular, bio-based systems	The results will be shared in D2.1 which is a public report

¹⁵ Retrieved from: <https://www.cessda.eu/Research-Infrastructure/Training/Expert-Tour-Guide-on-Data-Management/5.-Protect/Anonymisation>

4	Improving knowledge for assessing specific aspects of the sustainable transition	The results will be shared in 2 reports, Deliverable 2.2 and 2.3 which are both public reports
5	Development of a framework to monitor and assess the benefits of the sustainable transition	The results will be shared in D2.4 which is a public report.
6	Selection and definition of case studies from four critical sectors and case study analysis	The results will be shared in D3.1 which is a public report.
7	Analysis of findings and derivation of main conclusions and recommendations	The results will be shared in 2 reports, Deliverable 3.3 and 3.4 which are both public reports
8	Development of policy portfolio scenarios will formulate scenarios as a primary input for the simulations, which will define the final input requirements	The results will be shared in D4.1, as a public report
9	Model simulation and validation of the results	Documentation of data sources will be provided within deliverable D4.2, which is a public report
10	Capacity building for local stakeholders Results of the activities will be reported in D5.4, as a public report. Additionally, other capacity-building materials will be made available as presentations, documentation or videos on the SUSTRACK website and during stakeholder engagement activities.	Results of the activities will be reported in D5.4, as a public report. Additionally, other capacity-building materials will be made available as presentations, documentation or videos on the SUSTRACK website and during stakeholder engagement activities.
11	Identification of policy priorities	Results of the activities will be reported in 2 public deliverables (D5.1 and D5.1 updated). Additionally, other materials will be made available as presentations, summary documents and Excel databases on the SUSTRACK website.
12	Policy recommendations for a sustainable transition towards a circular bio-based economy Results will be made available in D5.5 as a public report.	Results will be made available in D5.5 as a public report.
13	Setting up and Operation of SUSTRACK's Advisory Board	Data will be stored in a consortium cloud server.
14	Stakeholder Engagement activities, workshops and conferences	Data will be stored in a consortium cloud server.
15	Monitoring and assessment of Communication, Dissemination activities	Data will be stored in a consortium cloud server and will be used to fill the communication and dissemination templates on the EC participant portal.
16	Website and social media analytics	Quantitative data from website and social media analytics are anonymous and will be shared with the consortium, the EU Commission

		and the large public, if necessary.
17	Data collected from project events	Data collected from project events will be shared with the consortium, the EU Commission and the participants of the event upon the sign of a consent form.
18	Newsletter subscription	Data will be collected in a dedicated cloud server owned by FVA (communication and dissemination leader) in BlueiTech web farm (https://blueitech.com/). The data will only be used by the communications manager of the project and it won't be shared with anyone else. Quantitative data will be extracted from it to share the analytics with the project partners. Permission to manage the data was provided at the time of collecting it.
19	The development and calibration of the simulation model	A documentation of data sources will be provided within deliverable D4.2, which is a public report.

3.2.3 Methods, software tools and documentation to access the data

SUSTRACK emphasises the accessibility of the data collected/generated during the project. With that in mind, no specialised method, software tool and/or documentation is expected to be needed at the moment, in order to access the data. Stakeholders will have the ability to access the data by simply using their web browser (e.g. Mozilla, Google Chrome, Internet Explorer, Safari, etc.) through their computers (either desktop or laptop), smartphones and/or tablets.

More specifically, they first need to access EOSC through its webpage (following the link <https://eosc-portal.eu/>) and utilise the search engine of the repository to search for interesting data. By typing the name of the project (or any other relevant keyword connected to the SUSTRACK data) the search engine will direct the user to the project's data, ready to be explored and re-used. Moreover, since the data will be available in open formats, we will be ensuring that they can appropriately be read by a range of different softwares that are widely and freely accessible to all potential users of the data.

Closed data will only be accessed by authorised project partners through the usage of a cloud storage service. Again, no specialised method, software tool and/or documentation is needed to this end.

3.2.2 Data, metadata, and data integrity

SUSTRACK's open data along with their linking metadata as well as any relevant code and documentation (if applicable) required to access these data, will be deposited to and securely stored by EOSC. It is quite unlikely that EOSC will terminate its operation and stop providing its services, but in such a case all data, metadata, code and documentation uploaded will be transferred and hosted to other suitable repositories without undue delay. In this respect, it is

important to note that, since all of SUSTRACK's openly available data will make use of PIDs (i.e., DOIs), the links to the data will not be affected. In parallel, the project's data that will not be openly available for sharing will be deposited, together with their accompanying metadata, code and documentation (if necessary), to the cloud web storage service employed by the project.

3.2.3 Restrictions

By utilising EOSC for sharing the project's openly available data, SUSTRACK can apply **different levels of accessibility** for this data taking into account any relevant issues (such as ethics, rules of personal data, intellectual property, commercial, privacy-related, security-related, etc.).

More specifically, **EOSC offers the following levels of data accessibility:**

- **Open access:** Data remains available for re-use. Nevertheless, the level at which this data can be re-used is determined also by their accompanied licence for re-use (see subsection 3.4.1).
- **Embargoed status:** Access to the data will be restricted until the end of the embargo period, at which time, the content will automatically become publicly available.
- **Restricted access:** The data will not be made publicly available and sharing will be made possible only by the approval of the project partner that has the responsibility of the data.
- **Closed access:** The data is protected against unauthorized access at all levels and only members of the consortium have the right to access it.

Project partners will mainly use the open access level to disseminate the project's data amongst the interested stakeholders. Nevertheless, in some cases embargo periods or restricted access may be used as described in Subsection 3.2.1. Data that will not be available for re-use will be accessible only by authorised partners of SUSTRACKS's consortium and /or authorised personnel from the European Commission.

Moreover, **SUSTRACK will ensure open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications** that may be produced in the framework of the project. In particular, according to the Grant Agreement, SUSTRACK will ensure that:

- at the latest at the time of publication, a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication is deposited in a trusted repository for scientific publications
- immediate open access is provided to the deposited publication via the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or a licence with equivalent rights; for monographs and other long-text formats, the licence may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g., CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND) and
- information is given via the repository about any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication.

Beneficiaries (or authors) must retain sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with the open access requirements.

Metadata of deposited publications must be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent, in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable) and provide information at least about the following: publication (author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue); Horizon Europe; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the publication.

Only publication fees in full open-access venues for peer-reviewed scientific publications are eligible for reimbursement.

Along these lines, this section has provided the methodology applied in the frame of Sustrack to ensure that its data are as openly accessible as possible by any stakeholder that may find it interesting for re-use. In this context, Sustrack also focuses on providing metadata standards and appropriate metadata vocabularies to increase data interoperability. The following section provides further details in this respect.

3.3 Making data interoperable

Data interoperability refers to the ability of systems and services that create, exchange and use data to have clear, shared expectations for the contents, context and meaning of that data¹⁶. With that in mind, Sustrack has adopted in its data management methodology the use of metadata vocabularies, standards and methods that will increase the interoperability of the data collected/generated through its activities.

More specifically, **the interoperability of the data that will not be publicly shared will be facilitated by the use of the Dublin Core Metadata standard.** This standard is a small “metadata element set” which accounts for issues that must be resolved in order to ensure that data meet traditional standards for quality and consistency, while still remaining broadly interoperable with other data sources in the linked data environment. The fifteen elements of the standard provide a vocabulary of concepts with natural-language definitions (e.g., title, creator, author, etc.) that are instantly converted into open machine-readable formats (such as XML, HTML, etc.), enabling machine-processability. Each element is optional and may be repeated, while the standard itself offers ways exist for refining them, encouraging the use of encoding and vocabulary schemes. The vocabulary of the Dublin Core Metadata standard is presented in the following table¹⁷:

Table 5: Dublin Core Metadata standard vocabulary

No	Element	Element definition
1	Title	A name given to the resource.
2	Creator	An entity primarily responsible for making the content of the resource.

¹⁶ L. Steele & T. Orrell (2017). The frontiers of data interoperability for sustainable development. Publish What You Fund and Development Initiatives

¹⁷ Sugimoto, S., Baker, T., & Weibel, S. L. (2002). Dublin Core: Process and Principles. Lecture Notes in Computer Science Digital Libraries: People, Knowledge, and Technology, 25-35.

3	Subject	The topic of the content of the resource.
4	Description	An account of the content of the resource.
5	Publisher	An entity responsible for making the resource available.
6	Contributor	An entity responsible for making contributions to the content of the resource.
7	Date	A date associated with an event in the life cycle of the resource
8	Type	The nature or genre of the content of the resource.
9	Format	The physical or digital manifestation of the resource.
10	Identifier	An unambiguous reference to the resource within a given context.
11	Source	A reference to a resource from which the present resource is derived.
12	Language	A language of the intellectual content of the resource.
13	Relation	A reference to a related resource.
14	Coverage	The extent or scope of the content of the resource.
15	Rights	Information about rights held in and over the resource.

Along similar lines, the interoperability of openly available data will be facilitated through EOSC, since its metadata will be stored internally in JSON format according to a defined JSON schema. This encloses HTML microdata that allows machine-readable data to be embedded in HTML documents in the form of nested groups of name-value pairs. Moreover, the JSON schema provides a collection of shared vocabularies in microdata format that can be used to mark up pages in ways that can be understood by the major search engines. Moreover, all metadata linked to the open data is exported via the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) and can be harvested. The OAI-PMH develops and promotes interoperability standards that facilitate the efficient dissemination of data amongst diverse communities¹⁸.

¹⁸ Corrado, E.M. (2005) 'The importance of open access, open source, and open standards for libraries', Issues in Science and Technology Librarianship.

3.4 Increase data re-use

3.4.1 License schemes to permit the widest use possible

The application of a licence to SUSTRACK open data is a simple way to ensure that any interested third party can re-use it. In this context, licences are the instruments which permit a third party to copy, distribute, display and/or modify the project's data only for the purposes that are set by the licence. Licences typically grant permissions on conditions that certain terms are met. While the precise details vary, three conditions are commonly found in licences which are attribution, non-derivative, and non-commerciality.

Along these lines, SUSTRACK publishes openly available data under the Creative Commons licencing scheme to foster their re-use and build an equitable and accessible environment for them. EOSC provides SUSTRACK with the opportunity to publish its open data under five Creative Common licences as follows:

- Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 4.0 (CC BY-SA 4.0) according to which any third party can freely copy, distribute, display and modify the datasets for any purpose. Remix, transform, or built upon data, must be distributed under the same license as the original. Third parties must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made.
- Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) according to which any third party can freely copy, distribute, display and modify the datasets for any purpose. Third parties must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made.
- Creative Commons Attribution-No Derivatives 4.0 International (CC BY-ND 4.0) during which any third party can freely copy, distribute, display and modify the datasets for any purpose. Remix, transform, or built upon data, however, must not be distributed. Third parties must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made.
- Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International (CC BY-NC 4.0) based on which third parties can copy, distribute, display and modify the datasets for any purpose other than commercial unless they get permission from project partners first. Third parties must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made.
- Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives 4.0 International (CC BY-NC-ND 4.0) according to which third parties can copy, distribute, display and modify the datasets for any purpose other than commercial unless they get permission from project partners first. Remix, transform, or built upon data, however, must not be distributed. Third parties must give appropriate credit, provide a link to the license, and indicate if changes were made.

Figure 1: CC BY-SA 4.0

Figure 2: CC BY 4.0

Figure 3: CC BY-ND 4.0

Figure 4: CC BY-NC 4.0

Figure 5: CC BY-NC-ND

Different licensing schemes may be selected to better fit the need of SUSTRACK's open data ensuring not only their long-term preservation and re-use but also the interests of the consortium along with the rights of individuals for whom the data is about. In such a case, this subsection of the DMP will be updated accordingly.

3.4.2 Availability for re-use

The re-use of data is a key component of SUSTRACK's methodology for making data FAIR. In fact, making data available for re-use ensures interested stakeholders, other than project partners, can benefit from this data, contributing towards maximising the impact of the project. Rich metadata created based on metadata standards that enable proper discovery as well as appropriate licensing schemes facilitate the re-use of SUSTRACK's open data, allowing them to find valuable utility.

In principle, it is expected that data will become available for re-use no later than 120 days after the end of its processing in the framework of the project (i.e., collection, anonymisation, aggregation, etc.) to ensure that any additional data management activities required to this end do not compete with the timely delivery of the project's planned outputs.

With that in mind, the expected time that SUSTRACKS's data will be made openly accessible and uploaded to EOSC is indicatively provided in the following table:

Table 6: Expected time that data will be made open through EOSC

No	Data	Expected time for making data open	Notes
1	Gap analysis	30/04/2024	After the interim report (M18)
2	Multi-stakeholder consultation and validation of the limits of the linear, carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy	30/04/2024	After the interim report (M18)
3	Review of knowledge to monitor and assess the benefits of the transition to circular, bio-based systems	2023	None
4	Improving knowledge for assessing specific aspects of the sustainable transition	31/10/2025	After the final report (M36)
5	Development of a framework to monitor and assess the benefits of the sustainable transition	30/10/2023	None
6	Selection and definition of case studies from four critical sectors and case study analysis	30/04/2024	After the interim report (M18)
7	Analysis of findings and derivation of main conclusions	31/10/2025	After the final report (M36)

	and recommendations		
8	Development of policy portfolio scenarios will formulate scenarios as a primary input for the simulations, that will define the final input requirements	31/01/2024	None
9	Model simulation and validation of the results	01/05/2025	Organizing online webinars (involving at least 20 stakeholders, each) to transfer knowledge and support further applications of the model
10	Capacity building for local stakeholders	31/07/2025	None
11	Identification of policy priorities	31/12/2023	None
12	Policy recommendations for a sustainable transition towards a circular bio-based economy	31/10/2025	None
13	Setting up and Operation of Sustrack's Advisory Board	30/04/2023	After the first meeting of AB.
14	Stakeholder Engagement activities, workshops and conferences	30/04/2024	After the interim report (M18)
15	Monitoring and assessment of Communication, Dissemination activities	30/04/2024	After the interim report (M18) and after the final report (M36)
16	Website and social media analytics	30/04/2024-31/10/2025	After the interim report (M18) and after the final report (M36)
17	Data collected from project events	30/04/2024-31/10/2025	After the interim report (M18) and after the final report (M36)
18	Newsletter subscription	30/04/2024-31/10/2025	After the interim report (M18) and after the final report (M36)
19	Data collected from dissemination and communication actions	30/04/2024-31/10/2025	After the interim report (M18) and after the final report (M36)

4. DATA QUALITY ASSURANCE

Quality Assurance (QA) and Quality Control (QC) activities are an integral part of Sustrack's data management methodology and are implemented prior to the publication of any data to EOSC, safeguarding the transparency, consistency, comparability, completeness and accuracy of the data.

QA is a planned system of review procedures conducted outside the framework of developing a dataset, by personnel not directly involved in the dataset development process¹⁹. In the context

¹⁹ 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories, Vol. 1 General Guidance and Reporting, CHAPTER 6 Quality Assurance / Quality Control and Verification.

of SUSTRACK, it takes the form of **peer-reviews of methods and/or data summaries** to assess the quality of the dataset and identify any need for improvement, ensuring that the dataset correctly incorporates the scientific knowledge and data generated.

QC is defined as a system of checks to assess and maintain the quality of the dataset being compiled²⁰. The relevant procedures of SUSTRACK are designed to provide routine technical checks as they measure and control data consistency, integrity, correctness and completeness as well as identify and address errors and omissions. In this context, QC checks cover everything from data acquisition and handling, the application of approved procedures and methods, and documentation. Some of the general quality checks undertaken in the framework of the project include checking (i) for transcription errors in data input; (ii) that scale measures are within the range of acceptable values; and (iii) whether proper naming conventions are used.

5. OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS

5.1 KE Srl Green Economy Model (GEM)

For the SUSTRACK project, the Green Economy Model (GEM) will be used and enhanced to include bio-based dynamics required for analysing the case study sectors. The software used for the development and parameterization of the model is Vensim DSS. GEM is used to analyze the systemic impacts of transitioning towards a more bio-based economy, based on case study inputs and the formulation of scenarios. For this purpose, a baseline simulation as well as multiple transition scenarios will be simulated, which allows for the comparative assessment of impacts across socioeconomic and environmental performance indicators. For this purpose, GEM will be informed mainly by the case study analysis (WP3) and related findings as well as the scenarios defined in WP4 (T4.1), but also consider the knowledge and data developed in WP1 and WP2 to ensure that sectoral as well as macro-dynamics related to a bio-based economy are captured correctly.

Cross-sectoral analysis of policy impacts: The simulation of scenarios until 2050 or 2060 allows for analysing how the system performs in the presence and absence of policies that facilitate the transition towards a bio-based economy or bio-based alternatives.

The comparison of the transition scenarios against the baseline scenario allows the assessment of economy-wide benefits and drawbacks induced by policy interventions. GEM forecasts macroeconomic indicators such as GDP, employment and emissions, estimates the additional investment required to enable the transition and quantifies and monetizes externalities. This allows for the development of a system-wide cost-benefit analysis that integrates the additional investment required, avoided costs as well as added benefits into one framework of analysis.

Stakeholders regarding the Green Economy Model include partners and external parties such as policymakers, academia, and professional networks. Partners, specifically WP5, are involved in the identification of policy priorities and the definition of policy action. The external stakeholders are interested in the data and its implications for their respective fields. The format and size of the data include .mdl files of approximately 5 MB, .vdf files of around 800 MB per simulation, and .xlsx files of approximately 1-5 MB per output file. The data will be stored offline in Excel spreadsheets and can be made available using Google Drive or Dropbox.

²⁰ 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories, Vol. 1 General Guidance and Reporting, CHAPTER 6 Quality Assurance / Quality Control and Verification.

The model, its documentation, and simulation outputs will be published in public reports as deliverables of tasks T4.2 and T4.3, ensuring open access to the data. The timing for making data available will be after the scenarios are simulated and validated with project partners and stakeholders.

However, the FAIR management principles for the dedicated research output are yet to be determined. The general principles (see section 3.) will ensure that the data is findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable, thus promoting transparency, collaboration, and accountability.

6. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

6.1 Estimated costs for making data FAIR

The costs required for making the data collected/generated during SUSTRACK's activities compliant with FAIR principles are integrated into the budget of the project. With that in mind, the table which follows provides an overview of the estimated costs of making data FAIR as well as their budget source within the framework of SUSTRACK.

In order to produce the estimations of the costs for making data FAIR in the context of SUSTRACK, a series of **assumptions** were made, taking into account the respective **guidelines** provided by the Research Data Management Support, a multidisciplinary network of data experts within Utrecht University²¹, as well as of the UK Data Service and its data management costing tool²². With that in mind, the estimated costs for making SUSTRACK's data FAIR cover **data-related activities and resources across the data lifecycle**, spanning from collection and documentation through storage and preservation over to sharing and re-use.

In particular, costs for **data collection** cover activities necessary for acquiring external datasets (if required), gathering/generating new data, transcribing (if applicable), formatting and organising this data as well as acquiring informed consent from data subjects. This data processing activity reflects the majority of the costs required for making data FAIR as the majority of SUSTRACK's data constitutes new data collected/generated over the course of the project. At the same time, **data documentation** costs address the effort required for describing data (e.g. marking data with variable and value labels, code descriptions, etc.) as well as creating well-defined metadata along with a meaningful description of the context and methodology of how data was collected/generated and processed (where necessary).

Costs for **data storage** include the resources required for ensuring adequate storage space for the data as well as the effort necessary for conducting data back-ups, while **data access and security** costs encompass costs related to ensuring access to the data as well as for protecting it from unauthorised access or use or from disclosure. Given that the storage of SUSTRACK's data will not require the procurement of additional space (other than what is already available to project partners) as well as that no special measures or software are required to access and secure the data (other than what is inherently built into the repositories of SUSTRACK's data), such costs are kept to a minimum.

²¹ Research Data Management Support. Guides: Costs of data management. Utrecht University. Retrieved from: <https://www.uu.nl/en/research/research-data-management/guides/costs-of-data-management>

²² UK Data Service. Costing Data Management. Retrieved from: <https://www.ukdataservice.ac.uk/manage-data/plan/costing>

Data preservation costs, on the other hand, are estimated relatively higher than data storage, access and security costs, as additional effort will be required in several cases in order to convert the collected/generated data from their original form (e.g. physical interview transcripts) to an open and/or machine-readable format suitable for long-term preservation (e.g. to an .xlsx format.). Adequate effort for **data availability and re-use** costs is also foreseen to safeguard the appropriate digitisation and anonymisation of the data as well as cover any resources required for data sharing and cleaning. Along the same lines, an appropriate effort is foreseen for **overall data management** as well, in order to cover the effort related to the operationalisation of data management in the framework of SUSTRACK.

Finally, costs for **long-term preservation** in the framework of SUSTRACK are assumed to be negligible, since the open data of the project will be hosted in the repository of EOSC free of charge.

6.2 Data management responsibilities

For the effective, proper and secure handling of the data collected/generated in the frame of SUSTRACK, specific data management roles have been established within the data management methodology and procedures of the project. These responsibilities are outlined in this section of the DMP and are as follows.

Project Coordinator: UNIT, is responsible for overall data management in the framework of SUSTRACK. PC is responsible for the elaboration of the DMP and its updates (when necessary along with the support of all partners). At the same time, the PC is responsible for the elaboration of proper templates for the Informed Consent Form and the Data Subject Request Form to be appropriately adjusted and utilised by project partners during the relevant activities of the project as well as for drafting the project's Privacy Policy that has been uploaded on the project's website. The PC in collaboration with the relevant project partners (e.g., Task Leaders) will examine if additional specific privacy policies are required for certain project tasks and will coordinate the elaboration of such privacy policies. Finally, the UNIT coordinates with Work Package Leaders, Task Leaders and Responsible Partners to determine whether and how the data collected/generated by the project are shared and become available for re-use, contributes to its quality assurance and uploads the project's openly available data to EOSC.

Work Package Leaders (WPLs): The WPL is responsible for coordinating the implementation of the data processing activities performed under the WPs they are leading. Moreover, they align with the PC and the respective Work Task Leader on whether and how the data gathered/produced under the tasks that fall within the WP they are leading will be shared and/or re-used. This includes the definition of access procedures as well as potential embargo periods along with any necessary software and/or other tools which may be required for data sharing and re-use. Finally, the WPLs are the main ones responsible for assuring the quality of the data stemming from the activities of the WP they are leading, including assessing their quality and indicating any need for improvement to the respective Work Task Leaders.

Work Task Leaders (WTLs): WTLs are responsible for the data collected/generated in the frame of the tasks that fall under their leadership as well as for safeguarding their appropriate and timely processing. Moreover, they are responsible for properly adjusting the Informed Consent Form and Data Subject Request Form templates, to the needs and specificities of the activities carried out in the task they are leading. WTLs are responsible for identifying the need for a specific privacy policy regarding the task they are leading and for collaborating with UNIT for drafting and releasing it to the public. Finally, they undertake any necessary actions to prepare the data collected/generated through the tasks they are leading for sharing either within the consortium

or openly (including the use of proper naming conventions, application of suitable anonymisation techniques, creation of appropriate metadata and documentation, etc.).

Partners: All project partners are tasked to collect, digitise, anonymise, store, destroy and/or otherwise process data for the specific purpose of the activity in which it has been collected/generated within the project. They are responsible for appropriately collecting the necessary consent for processing data as well as for ensuring that the Informed Consent Form and the Data Subject Request Form used to this end are properly adjusted to the needs of the activity they are participating (including references to the project’s Privacy Policy and any other applicable specific privacy policies) and, in any particularities, applicable to their organisation while ensuring adherence to provisions of relevant national data protection legislation in their respective country. Moreover, they are responsible for managing the consent forms they have collected with a view to demonstrating their compliance with the relevant applicable EU and national regulation(s). Finally, they perform quality checks to assess and maintain the quality of the dataset(s) held within their records.

Data repositories: Data repositories are tasked with the storage and long-term preservation of the project’s data. In this respect, EOSC will maintain and preserve the openly available data of SUSTRACK, enabling its sharing and re-use. To this end, EOSC assigns metadata and DOIs to the data, while also taking all necessary measures to securely back up the data and restore it, safeguarding its long-term preservation.

In this context, the following table illustrates the allocation of data management responsibilities amongst the members of the SUSTRACK consortium per data collected/generated under each WP.

Table 7: Data management responsibilities of SUSTRACK’s partners per data collected/generated under each WP

WP	WPL	Data	Task	WTL	Responsible partners
WP1	UNIT	Gap analysis	T1.1	UNIT	KE, UNIFE, BAM, TECNALIA, UGENT
		Multi-stakeholder consultation and validation of the limits of the linear, carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy	T1.2	BAM	UNIT, TECNALIA, UNIFE, PC, KE, FVA
		Co-creation focus group	T1.2.1	PEDAL	UNIT, TECNALIA, UNIFE, PC, KE, FVA
		Interviews and surveys	T1.2.2	BAM	UNIT, TECNALIA, UNIFE, PC, KE, FVA
WP2	TECNALIA	Review of knowledge to monitor and assess the benefits of the transition to circular, bio-based systems	T2.1	TECNALIA	DBFZ, KE, BAM, UNIFE, UNIT, WR, FVA, UGENT
		Improving knowledge for assessing specific aspects of the sustainable transition	T2.2	WR	CIRCE, FVA, DBFZ, KE, TECNALIA, UNIT
		Development of a framework to monitor and assess the benefits	T2.3	TECNALIA	FVA, DBFZ, BAM, UNIT, WR, KE, PEDAL

		of the sustainable transition			
WP3	WR	Selection and definition of case studies from four critical sectors and case study analysis	T3.1	BAM	All Partners
		Analysis of findings and derivation of main conclusions and recommendations	T3.4	WR	UGENT, UNIT, CIRCE, PC, KE, TECNALIA, DBFZ, BAM
WP4	KE	Development of policy portfolio scenarios will formulate scenarios as a primary input for the simulations, that will define the final input requirements	T4.1	DBFZ	UNIT, BAM, WR, TECNALIA, KE, UNIFE, PC, UGENT
		Model simulation and validation of the results	T4.2	KE	WR, TECNALIA, BAM, FVA
WP5	DBFZ	Capacity building for local stakeholders	T5.2	DBFZ	All Partners
		Identification of policy priorities	T5.1	WR	UNIT, DBFZ, CIRCE, PC, FVA, KE, BAM, TECNALIA
		Policy recommendations for a sustainable transition towards a circular bio-based economy	T5.3	DBFZ	UNIT, WR, BAM, TECNALIA, PC, FVA, KE
WP6	FVA	Setting up and Operation of SUSTRACK's Advisory Board	T6.2	PC	All partners
		Stakeholder Engagement activities, workshops and conferences	T6.2	PC	All Partners
		Monitoring and assessment of Communication, Dissemination activities	T6.1	FVA	All Partners

7. DATA SECURITY

SUSTRACK will securely handle any collected/generated data throughout its entire lifecycle as it is essential to safeguard these data against accidental loss and/ or unauthorised access. To achieve this the project will apply appropriate technical and organisational measures based on a risk assessment of the relevant data that takes into account the impact and the likelihood of a potential data breach. With that in mind, the project's data security strategy aims at minimizing the probability that a data breach will occur during the course and after the completion of SUSTRACK, either from human error or hardware failure, as well as inhibiting any unauthorised access. Particularly, in the case of personal data collection/generation, it is crucial that these **data can only be accessible by those authorised to do so**. In case of unauthorised access or stolen data, the provisions of the Grant Agreement apply.

All project partners are responsible for processing²³ data using appropriate means, such as private servers or cloud service providers that adhere to the relevant legal data protection requirements (e.g., GDPR) and will ensure that these **data are protected**, and any **necessary data security controls have been implemented**, to minimize the risk of information leak and destruction. This case refers to the data that will be closed and therefore will not be shared and/or re-used within the framework of the project. In this case, to minimize the consequences of potential data losses, the data will be **backed up at regular time intervals based on change frequency and criticality**. **The backed-up files will be stored in appropriate storage media including external hard drives, flash drives, NAS devices and reputable cloud services**, so as to safeguard their preservation, while also enabling their recovery at any time. Moreover, **integrity checks**²⁴ will be carried out regularly ensuring that the stored data have not been changed or corrupted.

Access to closed data will only be permitted to authorised project partners. In case there is a **personal data breach**, the responsible **project partner will notify, without undue delay** and, where feasible, not later than **72 hours after having become aware of it, its competent national supervisory authority** (e.g., data protection authority) **as well as the data subject(s) that may be affected by the breach**. Moreover, the responsible partner will document any personal data breaches, including information such as the facts relevant to the breach, its effects and the remedial action(s) taken.

Identification and authentication access controls play an important role in the context of the project, as they help partners to protect the data collected/generated during SUSTRACK and especially personal data. To this end, each project partner is responsible for and committed to ensuring the application of appropriate access controls to the data they are processing. At the same time, **technical access controls are built into the SUSTRACK website and will be built into the setting out clear roles with access rights to the data stored there**, so that only authorised personnel have access. Specific project partners will be provided with unique accounts containing one or more roles assigned to them and at the same time enforcing role-based security when its staff processes the project's data. These accounts are expected to be username/password protected, maximising access control. Finally, in order to safeguard the privacy of the users of the SUSTRACK website dedicated **privacy policies** will define the way in which these online spaces collect, process and use personal data, the security procedures followed, the users' rights as well as the cookies policy employed.

On another note, openly available data will be stored safely for long-term preservation on EOSC. Both data files and metadata are kept in multiple online replicas and independent replicas ensuring their long-term preservation as well as their recovery when necessary. Moreover, for each file, two independent MD5 checksums are stored. One checksum is stored by INVENIO, used to detect changes to files made from outside of it whereas the other checksum is stored by EOS, and used for automatic detection and recovery of file corruption on disks. In this context, access control is applied by the different levels of openness that EOSC allows (i.e., open, embargoed, restricted and closed).

²³ Processing, according to Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament (General Data Protection Regulation), means any operation or set of operations which are performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction.

²⁴ An integrity check is the process of comparing the current state of stored data and/or programs to a previously recorded state in order to detect any changes.

8. ETHICS AND OTHER ISSUES

This Chapter addresses the ethical aspects of SUSTRACK's Data Management Plan and the ethical compliance of the underlying data foreseen to be collected/generated under the project's activities. The project will process data that is not included in any special category of personal data (i.e., non-sensitive data) according to the relevant data protection legislation (e.g., GDPR). In accordance with **Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 (GDPR)**, all personal data processed for the project's activities shall be:

- processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject;
- collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes relative to the project's objectives and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes;
- adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary for relation to the purposes for which they are processed;
- accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date;
- kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed;
- processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the personal data (see section 6).

For all personal data processing activities within the framework of the project, at least one lawful basis as of Art. 6 GDPR applies. Where informed consent is chosen as the lawful basis for processing, all relevant provisions of the data protection legislation (e.g., Art.7 GDPR) are observed. The project's Privacy Policy and the templates of the Informed Consent Form and the Data Subject Request Form, used in the implementation of the project's activities, are compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation and annexed to this DMP (see Annex II and Annex III). Last but not least, **no transfer of personal data outside the EU is foreseen as part of the project's implementation**. In the case of data storage providers situated both inside and outside the EEA, partners are committed to ensuring their compliance with the relevant GDPR requirements before start using their services.

It is important to highlight that **each partner is responsible for ensuring that the templates for the Informed Consent Form and Subject Data Request Form (including references to the project's Privacy Policy and any other applicable specific privacy policies) are appropriately adjusted** according to (i) the needs of the activity for which they are being used by them as well as to (ii) the relevant data protection laws and regulations applicable to their respective countries and/or organisation. **All partners should keep records to demonstrate that data subjects have consented to the processing of their personal data** and use consent management mechanisms that make it easy for individuals to withdraw their consent.

Finally, **no other national/funder/sectoral/departmental procedures for data management were used in the framework of SUSTRACK**.

9. CONCLUSIONS AND WAY FORWARD

This initial version of the SUSTRACK DMP aims at safeguarding the sound management of the data collected, processed and/or generated during the project's activities across their entire lifecycle, while also making them FAIR. It describes all the underlying processes of the SUSTRACK data management, collection, process and generation, in accordance with the GDPR guidelines, and sheds light on (i) the data being collected, processed and/or generated under the project activities, (ii) the specific objectives under which each dataset is collected, processed and/or generated, (iii) the allocation of resources and data management responsibilities and (iv) the data security and ethical aspects of the data.

In the framework of SUSTRACK, the DMP is a living document and is updated throughout the course of the project, considering its latest developments and available results. It is expected to be further developed and updated at least once at the end of the project (i.e., as D7.1 by M6 and as D7.2 by M36). If necessary, additional *ad-hoc* updates may be realised in order to include new data, better detail and/or reflect modifications in the methodologies applied or other aspects relevant to data management (such as costs for making data FAIR, size of data, etc.), changes in consortium policies and plans or other potential external factors.

10. ANNEXES

Annex I Privacy Policy

Within this Annex, the reader can find the draft project's overall Privacy Policy, which is uploaded on the project's website. Task leaders are responsible for developing any additional privacy policy needed in their tasks and activities in close collaboration with the UNITELMA. Moreover, they are responsible for appropriately adjusting and translating the templates to fit the needs and specificities of their task's activities.

Privacy Policy

LAST UPDATE: 07.02.2023

1. Who we are

SUSTRACK is a three-year project aimed at supporting policymakers in their efforts to develop sustainable pathways to replace fossil and carbon-intensive systems with sustainable circular and biobased systems at the EU and regional scale, contributing to achieving the European Green Deal's objectives.

Within the framework of SUSTRACK project, accessible from <https://www.sustrack.eu>, one of our main priorities is the privacy of our visitors. This Privacy and Cookies Policy document contains types of information that is collected and recorded by SUSTRACK project and how we use it. If you have additional questions or require more information about our Privacy and Cookies Policy, do not hesitate to contact us.

The partners of the SUSTRACK consortium, listed below, process certain types of personal data for the purposes of the project. Each partner is responsible for the personal data they collect and process during their activities under the framework of the project:

- UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI ROMA UNITELMA SAPIENZA
- STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH
- KNOWLEDGE SRL
- PEDAL CONSULTING SRO
- DBFZ DEUTSCHES BIOMASSEFORSCHUNGSZENTRUM GEMEINNUTZIGE GMBH
- UNIVERSITEIT GENT
- FUNDACION TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION

- FVA SAS DI LOUIS FERRINI & C
- UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI FERRARA
- BUNDESANSTALT FUER MATERIALFORSCHUNG UND - PRUEFUNG
- FUNDACION CIRCE CENTRO DE INVESTIGACION DE RECURSOS Y CONSUMOS ENERGETICOS

For further information, we can be contacted at: communication@sustrack.eu

2. How we collect your personal data?

We collect personal data both directly and indirectly:

Directly. We obtain personal data directly from individuals in a variety of ways, including but not limited to the following cases:

- an individual subscribes to our newsletter/s;
- an individual registers to attend meetings and events we host and during attendance at such events;
- we establish cooperative relationships with an individual;
- we provide professional services pursuant to our contract with the European Commission;
- an individual participates in an interview or survey organized by us.

Indirectly. We obtain personal data indirectly about individuals from a variety of sources, including:

- our research partners;
- our networks and contacts;
- public and open data sources such as public registers, news articles and internet searches;
- social and professional networking sites (e.g., LinkedIn).

3. What type of data we collect?

We only collect the data that are necessary for the smooth implementation of our project. These data fall into the following categories:

- contact details (name/ surname, e-mail address, street address, mobile phone number, land line phone number);

- professional information (job title, organization, field of expertise);
- demographics (e.g., age, gender, nationality);
- information about what a person knows or believes.
- videos and photos (from people that attend our events).

4. Basis of lawful processes

We process personal data on the following legal bases:

Legal obligations - for processing activities required for compliance both with applicable national and European legislation as well as with the specific legal and regulatory framework of the Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation of the European Union.

Consent - for processing activities such as organization of surveys and interviews, completing of questionnaires and dissemination of project's results.

Contractual obligations - for processing activities such as reporting to the European Commission and complying with project's publicity obligations.

5. What we do with your personal data?

We process your personal data with the purpose of:

- Conducting research (e.g., interviews, surveys);
- Dissemination our project's results to different types of stakeholder;
- Sending invitations and providing access to guests attending our events and webinars;
- Administering, maintaining, and ensuring the security of our information systems, applications, and websites;
- Processing online requests or queries, including responding to communications from individuals;
- Complying with contractual, legal, and regulatory obligations.

6. How we secure your personal data when we process it?

We continuously apply a personal data risk assessment process to identify, analyse, and evaluate the security risks that may threaten your personal data. Based on the results of this risk assessment, we define and apply a set of both technical and organizational measures to mitigate the above security risks, including but not limited to:

- Data Protection Policies to guide our personnel when processing your data;
- Written contracts with organizations that process personal data on our behalf;
- Non-Disclosure Agreements with our personnel;
- Back up process, antimalware protection, access control mechanisms, etc.
- Some of our partners have appointed a Data Protection Officer.

7. Do we share personal data with third parties?

We may occasionally share personal data with trusted third parties to help us deliver efficient and quality services. When we do so, we ensure that recipients are contractually bound to safeguard the data we entrust to them before we share the data. We may engage with several or all the following categories of recipients:

- Parties that support us as we provide our services (e.g., cloud-based software services such as Dropbox, Microsoft SharePoint, Google);
- Our professional advisers, including lawyers, auditors, and insurers;
- Dissemination services providers (e.g., MailChimp);
- Law enforcement or other government and regulatory agencies or other third parties as required by, and in accordance with applicable law or regulation;
- The European Commission according to our relevant contractual obligations.

SUSTRACK project's Privacy Policy does not apply to other advertisers or websites. Thus, we are advising you to consult the respective Privacy Policies of these third-party ad servers for more detailed information. It may include their practices and instructions about how to opt-out of certain options. You can choose to disable cookies through your individual browser options. To know more detailed information about cookie management with specific web browsers, it can be found at the browsers' respective websites.

8. Do we transfer your personal data outside the European Economic Area?

We do not own file servers located outside the European Economic Area (EEA). However, some partners may use cloud and / or marketing services from reputable providers such as SharePoint, DropBox, MailChimp, Google, etc., situated both inside and outside the EEA. We always check that such providers comply with the relevant GDPR requirements before start using their services.

9. General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

We are a Data Controller of your information and will retain your personal information only for as long as it is necessary for the purposes set out in this Privacy Policy. We will retain and use your information to the extent necessary to comply with our legal obligations, resolve disputes, and enforce our policies. If you are a resident of the European Economic Area (EEA), you have certain data protection rights. If you wish to be informed what Personal Information we hold about you and if you want it to be removed from our systems, please contact us. In certain circumstances, you have the following data protection rights:

- The right to access, update or to delete the information we have on you
- The right of rectification
- The right to object
- The right of restriction
- The right to data portability
- The right to withdraw consent

10. Log files

SUSTRACK project follows a standard procedure of using log files. These files log visitors when they visit websites. All hosting companies do this and a part of hosting services' analytics. The information collected by log files include internet protocol (IP) addresses, browser type, Internet Service Provider (ISP), date and time stamp, referring/exit pages, and possibly the number of clicks. These are not linked to any information that is personally identifiable. The purpose of the information is for analysing trends, administering the site, tracking users' movement on the website, and gathering demographic information.

11. Privacy Policies

You may consult this list to find the Privacy Policy for each of the advertising partners of SUSTRACK project. Third-party ad servers or ad networks uses technologies like cookies, JavaScript, or Web Beacons that are used in their respective advertisements and links that appear on SUSTRACK project, which are sent directly to users' browser. They automatically receive your IP address when this occurs. These technologies are used to measure the effectiveness of their advertising campaigns and/or to personalize the advertising content that you see on websites that you visit. Note that SUSTRACK project has no access to or control over these cookies that are used by third-party advertisers.

12. Children information

Another part of our priority is adding protection for children while using the internet. We encourage parents and guardians to observe, participate in, and/or monitor and guide their online activity. SUSTRACK project does not knowingly collect any Personal Identifiable Information from children under the age of 13. If you think that your child provided this kind of information on our

website, we strongly encourage you to contact us immediately and we will do our best efforts to promptly remove such information from our records.

13. Online Privacy Policy Only

Our Privacy Policy applies only to our online activities and is valid for visitors to our website with regards to the information that they shared and/or collect in SUSTRACK project. This policy is not applicable to any information collected offline or via channels other than this website.

14. Do we use cookies?

Our websites use cookies. Where cookies are used, a statement will be sent to your browser explaining the use of cookies. To learn more, please refer to our cookie policy.

Cookies are small text files which are saved on your computer, mobile phone or tablet. They allow the website to remember your actions and preferences (such as login, language, font size and other display preferences) so you don't have to keep re-entering them whenever you come back to the site. You can control and/ or delete cookies as you wish. If you do this, however, you may need to manually adjust your preferences every time you visit a site. For more information on how to manage cookies, please visit: <http://www.aboutcookies.org/>

15. Consent

By using our website, you hereby consent to our Privacy Policy and agree to its terms.

Annex II Informed Consent Form

Text in red colour contains guidelines for adjusting this template and should be deleted.

Text included in < > and/or highlighted with yellow should be replaced with content that is suitable to the context of each activity & project as well as to the organisation seeking to obtain the consent.

Before using this template take the time to carefully read and adjust it to the needs of the activity at hand as well as to any relevant regulations and particularities applicable to your country and organisation. Specifically, this template has been developed for a data processing activity involving interviews, however you can easily adapt it to other common data processing activities such as surveys, events organizing, etc.

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Who we are:

We are < Insert Partner Name > and we are contacting you in the framework of SUSTRACK, a project funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation funding programme. A detailed description on how SUSTRACK handles personal data is presented in the project's [Privacy Policy](#) that accompanies this Consent Form.

Project: SUSTRACK - Supporting the identification of policy priorities and recommendations for designing a sustainable track towards circular bio-based systems (GA Number 101081823).

Partner:

Organisation name: < Insert Partner Name >

Address: < Insert Partner Address >.

Phone: < Insert Partner Phone >.

E-mail: < Insert Partner Generic E-mail Address >

Responsible persons:

You may delete the line referring to the Data Protection Officer if your organisation does not have one.

#	Role	Name	E-mail
1	SUSTRACK Project Manager	<Insert name of project manager>	<Insert email of project manager>
2	Interviewer	<Insert name of interviewer>	<Insert e-mail of interviewer>
3	Data Protection Officer	<Insert name of DPO >	<Insert e-mail of DPO >

What do we need from you?

Please explain in a brief paragraph (4-5 lines) the activity and its purpose under the frame of the project.

Example: We need you to participate in an interview that will be carried out by SUSTRACK with a view to validate the limits of the linear, carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy.

The interview is expected to last for no more than < Insert number of minutes > minutes. We will take written notes and we will be making a sound recording of the interview.

Please adapt the following text to accurately depict the type of personal data to be collected.

To effectively conduct this interview, we need to process some of your personal data:

- Your contact details (full name, email, phone number);
- Some basic demographics (age, gender);
- Your professional info (organization, job position, field of expertise);
- Your opinions on the subject matter.

Why do we need your data & what will we do with them?

We need your data to contact you in order to plan and carry out the aforementioned interview and to resolve any ambiguities, questions and other issues that may arise after and as a result of the interview. We also need to record your data to keep track of the interview process. The project's deliverables that will be derived by the interview will not include your personal data or any other information that could identify you. Your personal data will remain on our written notes (interview's transcript) and/or the sound recording we will make during the interview.

We will share your data with a few other SUSTRACK project partners that are also involved in this task and will participate in the drafting of the relevant deliverables. We are also obliged to grant access to your data to:

- EU officials such as our Project Officer for purposes related to project's evaluation;
- EU agencies and other authorities for project's auditing purposes.

We would also be very happy if you gave us your consent to contact you in the future to ask you to participate in other project's activities (e.g., surveys, interviews, project events, SUSTRACK Advisory Board, etc.) and also to inform you about the project's progress (e.g., by sending you a newsletter or similar messages).

How can you withdraw your consent?

You should know that you can withdraw your consent at any time by communicating either on the phone or by email with the responsible persons listed in the previous page. With regards to the informational messages and newsletters you can always opt out by simply clicking the link "Unsubscribe" or something similar included at the end of all the relevant messages.

I hereby give my consent to the processing of my personal data needed for:

(Please, tick the boxes below to confirm that you give us your consent for the respective subject. Any boxes left unticked mean that you do not consent to the relevant subject.)

#	Consent Subject	Tick box
1	My participation in an interview that will be carried out by SUSTRACK to < insert key objective of the interview >	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	My participation in future activities of SUSTRACK	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Receiving newsletters and messages regarding SUSTRACK activities	<input type="checkbox"/>

Name of participant

Date

Signature

Annex III Data Subject Request Form

Text in red colour contains guidelines for adjusting this template and should be deleted.

Text included in < > and/or highlighted with yellow should be replaced with content that is suitable to the context of each activity & project as well as to the organisation seeking to obtain the consent.

SUSTRACK

Data Subject Request Form

You may delete the data referring to the Data Protection Officer if your organisation does not have one.

Contact

<Insert name of responsible Project Manager>

<Insert name of DPO > (Data Protection Officer)

<Insert email of responsible Project Manager>

<Insert e-mail of DPO >

Data Subject Request Form

This form should be used to submit a data subject request under the provisions of the European Union General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Submitter Details

Title:	
Name:	
Address:	

Type of Request

Please select the type of request you are making:

- Consent Withdrawal*
- Access request*
- Rectification of personal data*
- Erasure of personal data*
- Restriction of processing of personal data*
- Personal data portability request*
- Objection to processing of personal data*
- Request regarding automated decision making and profiling*

Personal data involved

Request details

Request reason/justification

Name:

Signature:

Date:

Once completed, this form should be submitted via e-mail to [< Insert contact e-mail of Partner >](#) or posted to:

[< Insert Partner Name >](#)

[< Insert Partner Address >](#)

Project Consortium

